

Ocean acoustic tomography, physical oceanographers, and scientific disagreement: An essay

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The advocacy for ocean acoustic tomography (Dushaw 2022), as a tool for scientific research or as a component of the global ocean observing system, and the opposition to this ocean observation approach, have presented the physical oceanographic community with a scientific disagreement. The disagreement over whether such measurements should be sustained has persisted for decades now, though common practice has been to ignore the disagreement. The resolution of such a disagreement is straightforward, prescribed by basic standards of scientific discourse. The issue could be readily resolved through careful, quantitative scientific analysis, with the conclusions published in high quality journals. The failure to resolve the question, and ***it is not resolved after decades***, points to a weakness in the science, a weakness that the world can presently ill-afford, given the dangers and challenges from climate change.

The spectrum of arguments pertaining to tomography over the past decades (the Table below gives examples) can perhaps be assessed with the aid of Graham's "Hierarchy of Disagreement" (Graham 2008). This hierarchy, given in a blogging essay by computer scientist and essayist Paul Graham, ranks the quality of an argument in a disagreement (Figure). Arguments like name calling, "ad hominem," and simple, dogmatic contradiction ("ipse dixit") are of low quality, while those like "finding the error in the opposing argument and explaining why it is mistaken" are of higher quality. Because higher quality arguments are more challenging and require more work, they are less common, and the hierarchy could be thought of as forming a pyramid, with the less common, quality arguments at the top. According to all the standards of scientific discourse I am aware of, professional scientists should in all cases engage in arguments in the upper tiers. Arguments in the lower tiers are not consistent with scientific standards, hence they are, by definition, unethical. Simple arguments such as "The Argo float system is all we need.", and similar, are examples of "ipse dixit" arguments. The lower-tier arguments that have been employed by those in opposition to tomography have been endless; this is the level of discourse I have experienced.

One of my motivations in writing this essay is because I wish I had been more cognizent of the nature and qualities of arguments earlier in my career. Being able to recognizing substandard arguments allows one to better respond, or at least have confidence that the opposition to one's ideas is not substantive.

In my career, I have tried to adhere to upper-tier arguments. In the early 1990s, there was a disagreement concerning the oceanic sound speed equation, that between the Chen-Millero and Del Grosso equations. We not only showed by data that the latter equation was more accurate, we also found the source of the error in the Chen-Millero analysis, and we published those results. After repeatedly hearing the assertion ("ipse dixit") that Argo obviates the need for tomography, I did a quantitative analysis to test that assertion in the North Atlantic, found that it was wrong, and published those results (Dushaw 2019). Note that in science, one does not have to disprove the hypotheses of

Figure 1: A schematic pyramid depicting a modified version of Graham's Hierarchy of Disagreement (Graham 2008). Arguments appropriate for professional scientists are refuting the central point, refutation, or counter argument. Such arguments are more refined and challenging to formulate, hence they are less common and toward the pinnacle of the triangle. Simple contradiction (ipse dixit), responding to tone, ad hominem, and name-calling are poor, fallacious arguments, hence they are toward the bottom of the triangle.

(Image modified from that on Wikipedia 2021, public domain.)

others. Our task is only to prove or disprove that our own hypotheses are correct, otherwise we will be reduced to endlessly chasing the erroneous hypotheses of others. Those that have advocated the hypothesis that Argo obviates the need for tomography have had a scientific obligation to provide data, argument, and publication to support that hypothesis. That hypothesis has no scientific support, however. And it has been refuted, subject to some future analysis or argument that shows otherwise.

There are other arguments than those of the original Graham's Hierarchy. One such argument could be ranked the lowest of any argument, which is to ignore the opposing view altogether, to deny the existence of the dispute. Another is to make a fictional or erroneous statement about the question at hand, and then spend the remaining argument discussing why the fictional statement is wrong. Often a counter argument gets short-circuited to a non-sequitur; in discussions regarding tomography, Argo proponents often quickly provide a defense of the Argo profiling float system. That is not the issue. Although I and others have pointed out deficiencies of that system, we do not question the existence of, or challenge the support for, Argo. I have heard countless poor forms of argument in opposition to acoustic thermometry. No doubt the possibilities for poor argument are endless, limited only by the creativity of Man.

The use of poor arguments has three basic aims: (1) to distract from the original issue, (2) to cause time and effort to be wasted, so that the original issue gets abandoned, and (3) to cause the opponent to second guess, or doubt, their position, that is, gaslighting. From experience, I've found that pointing out that an opponent's argument is substandard only seems to provoke anger. Someone employing substandard rhetoric is already essentially acting in bad faith; the situation is inherently irrational. In such a situation, it is wiser to consider who is the primary audience that one needs to convince; it is not likely to be the opponent with the substandard rhetoric.

A good "good faith" strategy in a disagreement is to repeat the objections of others, perhaps even reformulating them in a stronger fashion to avoid the "strawman" fallacy. Then provide quality counter arguments to refute the objections. In a recent publication (Dushaw 2022), I attempted this approach, but the mostly anecdotal arguments I repeated were of such poor quality (see Table) that reviewers deemed my approach entirely unacceptable. Those "seedy" arguments are the only ones available, however.

It is a truism that publications are important in science. When we talk to our peers or colleagues, they say, "If you want our respect, you must have publications." The administrations of our institutions regularly admonish us, "If you want pay raises and promotions, you must have publications." Our funding agencies similarly admonish us, "If you want to continue to receive grant funding, you must have publications." We require our doctoral students to publish their research in a dissertation and present a formal defense of the work. These requirements are because these are the standards of scientific discourse. Publications have such value, such currency, not only because they are the formal archive of the work, but also because they are how scientific disagreements formally get resolved. The reader may by now be overwhelmed by tedium, but I ask, finally: Why is it that with the world in climatological peril, when adherence to rigorous scientific standards is more important than ever, the publication standard with respect to ocean acoustic tomography has been thrown out the window? This is a plea to the oceanographic community to remedy the situation; the world deserves better.

REFERENCES

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Examples of Substandard Arguments Related to Ocean Acoustic Tomography

"Argument"	Comments
"You are the only one."	The original bad argument. There are many counter arguments, the most constructive being, "As a matter of logic, therefore, everyone has a valid argument that shows you are wrong. So what is it?"
"Dushaw would be better served collaborating with physical oceanographers."	An ad hominem argument, dismissive and denigrating. (Also wrong.)
"Why should I care about...[tidal vorticity], [internal tides]?"	A "Strawman" argument.
"If I wanted to measure internal tides, all I'd need is a thermistor!"	An "Ipse Dixit" argument. (Also wrong.)
"Dushaw should stop trying to convince the world that tomography can measure internal tides!"	Another version of "You are the only one". (Also wrong.)
With reference to tomography measuring ocean climate: "Argo gets that."	An "Ipse Dixit" argument. (Also wrong.)
"You won't have a career after Walter Munk passes away."	A horrible, discreditable statement. Of no scientific value. (Also wrong; it was made 26 years ago!)
"Proponents of tomography have a strange psychology."	An "Ad Hominem", together with "Name Calling", argument
"No need to look at the ATOC data! Let's move on!"	Dismissive out of "Arrogance". Unscientific.
Me: "Tomography measures the first internal wave mode." . . . P.O.#137: "No it doesn't."	P.O.#137 [Physical Oceanographer #137] makes an "Contradiction" statement.
"There is nothing that tomography can do that can't be done by other means."	Another "Ipse Dixit" statement. (Also wrong.) The reviewer who made this statement was asked to provide evidence to support it, but did not.